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CATALYTIC HYDROCHLORINATION OF PROPYLENE MIXED WITH ETHYLENE

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Abstract

The process of hydrochlorination of propylene mixed with ethylene, which can be used to purify ethylene from propylene impurities. Purity of ethylene after purification reaches 99.97%. Spectral methods for studying the catalyst and the valence state of chromium on silica gel: on the surface of the original catalyst 5% Cr/SiO₂ cations Cr³⁺ and Cr⁶⁺ belong to the category of chromium decachromate. It has been found that the selectivity catalyst in the process of hydrochlorination of propylene from a mixture with ethylene is determined the state of chromium in the acid structure. Replacing chromium with iron in the same weight concentrations on silicate does not allow for the purification of ethylene, since in this case ethylene hydrochlorination is observed in a wide temperature range.

Аннотация

Исследован процесс гидрохлорирования пропилена в смеси с этиленом, который может использоваться с целью очистки этилена от примесей пропилена. Чистота этилена после очистки достигает 99,97%. Спектральными методами изучен катализатор и установлено валентное состояние хрома на поверхности силикагеля: на исходном катализаторе 5% Cr/SiO₂ катионы Cr³⁺ и Cr⁶⁺ относятся к структуре декахромата хрома. Установлено, что селективность катализатора в процессе гидрохлорирования пропилена из смеси с этиленом определяется состоянием хрома в структуре кислоты. Замена хрома на железо в тех же весовых концентрациях на силикате не позволяет вести очистку этилена, так как при этом наблюдается гидрохлорирование этилена в широком интервале температур.

Keywords: Purification of ethylene, impurities, propylene, chromium silicon catalyst, spectral methods.

Ключевые слова: Очистка этилена, примеси, пропилен, хромкремниевый катализатор, спектральные методы.

It is known that in the production of ethylene in pyrolysis gases after distillation contains impurities of accompanying hydrocarbons, in particular propylene. Currently, in the industry for the purification of ethylene from propylene impurities is used concentrated sulfuric acid, which irreversibly absorbs propylene, which makes it difficult to dispose of the spent acid and leads to its significant consumption. In this regard, the development of a new method for purifying olefins instead of absorption is of undoubted interest. Previously, we have established an increased activity and selectivity of chromium-silicon oxide system in the formation of isopropyl chloride by vapor phase propylene hydrochlorination. It was also found that the researched catalyst does not conduct ethylene hydrochlorination. Therefore, we made an attempt to develop catalytic method of ethylene purification from propylene impurities by hydrochlorination the last one in the stream. This work is devoted to studying the regularities of this process and spectral features of the selective catalyst.

The catalyst was prepared by impregnating commercial silica gel (KSS brand) with aqueous solution of chromic anhydride of the appropriate concentration, followed by drying it in the air at 373-393 K for 2 hours.

The process was carried out in a flow type reactor under atmospheric pressure. Raw material - a mixture of ethylene, propylene and hydrogen chloride was fed into the reactor through a mixer. The reaction mixture was fed through a drexel to catch hydrogen chloride into a trap for freezing isopropyl chloride and into a gasometer.

Obtained products were analyzed chromatographically (LKhM-8MD chromatograph - thermal conductivity detector, carrier gas-hydrogen). To select the optimal conditions during the process, the temperature was varied within 293-493K, the contact time was 1-50 sec, the content of propylene in a mixture with ethylene 1-10 vol. %

The received results are presented in table 1 and in pic. 1,2.

Table 1

The degree of conversion of propylene from a mixture with ethylene

Propylene content in mixtures vol. %	Volumetric speed, hour ⁻¹	Conversion of propylene. %	Ethylene content after purification. %
1	1211	85,7	99,90
3,3	372	98,9	99,97
5,0	480	94,8	99,93
10,0	132	84,2	99,91

As it can be seen, increasing in temperature from 393-473 K sharply increases the degree of purification. Therefore, the most satisfactory results are achieved within 373-423 K at times contact 10-30 sec.

Pic. 1. Effect of temperature on the degree of purification of ethylene with reaction medium ($t=100^{\circ}\text{C}$)

Increasing the contact time to more than 10 sec has very little effect on the degree of cleaning ethylene, consequently, in terms of process productivity, a further increase contact time is beside the purpose.

Pic. 2. Dependence of the degree of purification of ethylene from contact time ($t=18^{\circ}\text{C}$) with reaction medium ($t=100^{\circ}\text{C}$)

As it can be seen, within the range of varying concentrations and contact time, the degree of conversion propylene to isopropyl chloride varies between 80-100%. With contact times 7 – 10 sec achieves almost complete extraction of propylene from a mixture with ethylene. Purity of ethylene after purification is 99.97% and can be increased by its recirculation.

When the content of chromium in the catalyst is more than 1 wt. % leakage observed side reactions, in addition, the active phase is carried away from the surface of the catalyst. It should be emphasized that the chromium-silicon oxide catalyst used practically does not lose its activity in this process.

In order to identify the nature of changes occurring on the surface catalyst as a result of the hydrochlorination of propylene mixed with ethylene Spectral studies of samples before and after work were carried out at various temperatures for 6 hours.

UV reflection spectra were recorded on a "Specord" device with an attachment. EPR spectra were recorded at 77 and 298 K on «Jeol» spectrometer.

UV diffuse reflectance spectrum of the original catalyst containing 0.5% chromium, is characterized by an intense complex absorption band with a maximum at interval 350-450 nm.

This band is responsible for electron transfer in the tetrahedron CrO_4^{2-} . Kink at 400 nm and a weak band with a maximum at 550-630 nm is attributed to electron transfer (d-d-transition) in Cr(III), which has an octahedral environment. Judging by the intensity of the absorption bands in the UV spectrum and the color of the original catalyst (yellow) on the surface of the system

under study, chromium is stabilized in the hexavalent form in CrO_4^{2-} the structure, which corresponds to literature data [1].

In the EPR spectrum of the initial catalyst containing 0.5% chromium, the signal of Cr^{3+} ions not found. It can be assumed that those responsible for the appearance of an inflection at 440 nm and a weak band at 570-630 nm in the UV reflectance spectrum is a distortion chromate ion CrO_4^{2-} as a result of interaction with hydroxyl groups of the surface silica gel or adsorbed water. After the operation of the catalyst in the process hydrochlorination of propylene in its UV spectrum, absorption is observed at 670-720 nm, indicating the formation of Cr^{3+} on the surface.

Table 2 compares the width and intensity of the resonant absorption lines Cr^{3+} cations in the EPR spectrum of catalysts. It can be observed, that at 298K the resonance absorption line (ΔH) of the Cr^{3+} cation of the catalyst after operation is 18000-18800 A/m. Cooling the sample leads to a narrowing of the line to 9600-10400 A/m. However, the intensity (J) of the signal increases unevenly. At room temperature, the ratio resonance absorption lines for catalysts after work in the process propylene hydrochlorination at 473 and 373 K is equal to 1, and at liquid nitrogen temperature -1.4. Apparently, on the surface of the researched catalyst, Cr^{3+} forms various composition and structure of aqua complexes, in connection with which the effects introduced into the EPR spectra thermal motion of water molecules, become noticeable when the catalysts are cooled [2- 5].

Table 2

Parameters of the Cr^{3+} signal in the EPR spectrum of the 0.5% Cr/SiO₂ catalyst

	Catalyst	g-factor		ΔH , A/m		J, rel. units	
		77K	293K	77K	293K	77K	293K
1	Initial	-	-	-	-	-	-
2	After working with 373K	2,03	2,03	9600	18000	156	70
3	After working with 473K	2,03	2,03	10400	18800	210	98

As a result of research, the process of hydrochlorination of propylene in a mixture with ethylene on chrome silicon catalyst, it was found that the selected catalyst can be used in purification of ethylene from propylene impurities. Ethylene purity after purification reaches 99.97%.

The complex of the considered data allow us to conclude, that at the initial in the 5% Cr/SiO₂ catalyst, the Cr³⁺ and Cr⁶⁺ cations belong to the structure of chromium decachromate. As a result of the propylene hydrochlorination reaction at 373 K, the transformation of the active mass leads to inhomogeneity in the coordination environment of chromium. Observed differences in the spectral manifestations of the original and spent catalysts are probably explained by the formation of chromium bichromate and chromate, as well as surface structures [6-9]. Lowering the temperature of phase transformations of chromic anhydride on SiO₂, apparently associated with exposure to propylene in an acidic environment.

Partial reduction of hexavalent chromium and the formation of new surface structures occur at the early stage of the process, but this does not significantly change the nature of the catalytic action of the system under study in the hydrochlorination reaction in the period after induction. The presence of air in the system causes the oxidation of propylene to acetone with the participation of adsorbed water. In the case of a continuous supply of air and water, together with propylene and hydrogen chloride, the general scheme of the catalytic reaction becomes more complicated; in this case, along with the target isopropyl chloride, the products of hydration and oxidation of olefins, in particular, isopropanol and acetone, are identified in the catalyst. The most favorable from the point of view of the implementation of these reactions is silica gel with a chromium content of 0.5%.

As a result of the research, it was found that the selectivity of the catalyst in the process of hydrochlorination of propylene from a mixture with ethylene is determined by the state of chromium in the acid structure. Replacing chromium with iron in the same weight concentrations on silicate does not allow for the purification of ethylene, since hydrochlorination is observed in this case ethylene over a wide temperature range.

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